

Gender equality in MULTISOURCE

In order to understand how gender is integrated and perceived in the daily work of MULTISOURCE partners, research was conducted in three categories: gender representation, Gender equality plans (GEP) and gender mainstreaming. In February 2024, data was collected on gender representation, as well as the responses to questions 1 – 6 in the gender mainstreaming section. In March 2024, during the MULTISOURCE Annual meeting in Milan, data available on pages 7 – 10 was obtained. Information on the Gender equality GEP was obtained in November 2024.

Gender balance

The questionnaire on gender representation and gender mainstreaming was carried out in February 2024 as a 2-staged survey among the 20 MULTISOURCE partners. The first part was an extension of the EC required gender-disaggregated data about the numbers of researchers and non-researchers in the consortium. An additional category was added to this survey, namely on gender-disaggregated data on work package and task leaders. In addition, the category non-binary was added to the categories men and women.

19 out of 20 partners answered the questionnaire, 1 not fully, so the statistics relates to 18 organisations that answered all the statistical questions

Everyone working at MS by gender

Researchers by gender

No of men researchers: 33
No of women researcher: 30
No of non-binary researchers: 6

Non-researchers by gender

No of men non-researchers: 17
No of women non-researchers: 32
No of non-binary non-researchers: 3

Work package / Task leaders by gender

No of men WP or task leaders in the project: 19
 No of women WP or task leaders in the project: 14
 No of non-binary WP or task leaders in the project: 2

Gender mainstreaming

The second part of the survey focused on gender mainstreaming as carried out by experts, carrying out various tasks in the project. Unlike the first part of the survey, which was filled by one representative per organisation, the second part was open to all persons involved in the project, with the aim of obtaining as many answers as possible. 29 persons provided some of the answers in the questionnaire, yet the majority was answered by 20 persons, and the final few by 18 persons.

1) Do you collect gender-disaggregated data?

No: 11 (55 % of answered)
 Sometimes: 5 (25 % of answered)
 Always: 4 (20 % of answered)
 Unanswered: 9

If you do not collect gender-disaggregated data or you do so only sometimes, why is this the case?

- Not sure when and where it is useful to do so
- In our task, which pertains only to administrative and organisational aspects, we mostly focus on institutions and more rarely on individuals regardless of their gender
- We do not collect data at all
- Not relevant for my research
- Our institution used to do this, but in our team we don't
- I do work with data which have gender, but I do not collect it and I do not work on any gender-disaggregated data in this project
- We only work with data of water sample quality. Gender-disaggregation does not apply.
- While Water Europe acknowledges the importance of gender-disaggregated data collection in many contexts, within the scope of our organization, it does not directly align with our primary goals and objectives.
- Many events are tours or presentations of our models and facilities to visitor groups for which we do not collect personal data.

- We collect this information by supporting our wp6 in the task related to gender and diversity.
- Sometimes we forgot, sometimes it is not relevant, sometimes not possible (gender has not been asked)
- We are not the office in charge of collecting gender data. We are trying to do it on environmental data that we manage

2) Have you at any stage of your work conducted a gender analysis, trying to understand if or how your NBS/tool will affect men and women?

No: 14 (70 % of answered)

Sometimes: 4 (20 % of answered)

Always: 2 (10 % of answered)

Unanswered: 9

If you have not conducted / only sometimes conduct a gender analysis, what could be the reasons for this, in your opinion? Please share a few thoughts below.

- Not sure when and where it is useful to do so
- We do not develop NBS tool (or any tool) in our task (x 2)
- We consider possible effects of what we design on humans mainly for estimating the social impact which often is linked to just leisure/fruition and usually that's done by distributing questionnaires to families, we do not even know who is compiling them; anyway in our phase of the work our concern are much more related to the impacts on the environment that on humans.
- Not relevant for my work
- We haven't done any analysis yet
- When we invited the stakeholders to share project results, such as during the workshops organized by us, we conducted a gender analysis of the invited people
- Sexuality is not really relevant to my work in this project.
- We have been discussing gender and chemical risk assessment.
- At this stage, the work at our organisation does not require the execution of any formal gender analyses. However, our organisation does have a diversity and inclusiveness plan that incorporates a gender equality plan. Our approach ensures inclusivity for all genders, and we continuously monitor for any gender-related considerations that may be necessary.
- This part of the work plan is covered by another partner.
- We do not know how to check for that.

- We analysed the social acceptance factors of the pilot and how they are influenced by gender. We did not analyze the technology selection tool in terms of gender.
- At least we have tried to think how the tool/NBS could affect different genders

3) *How often do you consult organisations or experts dealing with gender issues in your work?*

Never: 10 (50 % of answered)

Sometimes: 9 (45 % of answered)

Always: 1 (5 % of answered)

Unanswered: 9

If the answers were never or sometimes, what is your opinion about your organisation's practice and the reasons behind it?

- Not sure when and where it is useful to do so.
- The question of gender may appear from time to time regarding ethical issues in the projects. Our organisation can benefit from the support of its mother institution for these aspects. It has several contacts for ethics that we can consult if needed in the projects. However the thinking specifically on gender is not really developed inside INRAE and INRAE Transfert everyday practices.
- My organisation is strongly involved in gender equality. I have a positive opinion.
- I think persons in my lab think gender issues are not a problem whether because they do not experience it, whether because they think this is a "private" thing.... This is too bad.
- Apparently there is no need in our situation of a very small SME composed just by males up to few time ago when we have got on board our first female associate.
- Done if deemed relevant.
- Our institution is a big one, around 45 thousand people... There are programs dealing with gender issues.
- Sexuality is not really relevant to my work.
- Gender issues are a part of the discussions at an institutional level. It is something covered at different levels at the institute level. But not something we do directly connected with MULTISOURCE.
- Lately, we have been discussing with gender experts, as part of our efforts to ensure inclusivity, diversity, and address gender-related considerations in our work. While not a routine practice, we recognise the value of seeking their expertise on specific aspects of our work when needed.

- We consult experts on gender issues in questions where the need is most apparent, namely the development of innovative public toilets and/or agribusiness practices. We could certainly mainstream this more, but are definitely limited by our capacities as an SME.
- I do not understand the question. When I have a question regarding gender issues I can contact our organizations diversity office. I am usually satisfied with their suggestion or consultation.
- Internally there are initiatives that aim to integrate this topic in the company.
- We have some expertise within our organisation.
- I haven't consulted explicitly to the gender expert but they send us from time to time ideas, info etc. on how to take gender issues into account.
- We have an office to promote gender equality, but not in our environmental field.

4) When you conduct internal or external meetings, do you think about issues such as gender parity, making sure that men and women have the possibility to express their views equally and that all views are taken equally into consideration when making decisions?

Never: 2 (10 % of answered)

Sometimes: 5 (26 % of answered)

Always: 12 (63 % of answered)

Unanswered: 10

If the answers were never or sometimes, what could be the reasons for this, in your opinion? Please share a few thoughts below.

- Our work is entirely focused on organisation and administrative responsibilities. Women represent a large majority of the workforce in these two domains. There are no particular process or deep thinking based on gender for decision-making or expression of opinions in our work. However, the teams work in a horizontal way with no real hierarchy between individuals. My personal position provides me with a certain authority during external meetings. As much as I can, I try to be cautious and conscious of behavior that may prevent other people to express themselves. It is actually part of my work to make sure that everybody's opinion is known and taken into account.
- I do not find gender or sexuality to be relevant factors to consider with what they think. I do, however, find it pertinent to make an environment that ensures an inclusive dialog at any meeting I participate in.

- Many competing issues to focus on. As a woman I am conscious of this though, and have actively taken measures in meetings and also organisational restructuring to improve gender parity.
- Yes, it is thought that there should always be parity of gender and participation. However, there may be cases where you are simply part of a group of partners, people, who are already there and with whom you have to have meetings, and there may not be parity.
- Lack the tools and trained people to do so.

5) *Do you think it is important and/or relevant to mainstream gender into your work?*

- It is partially relevant. Our organisation is not involved in any scientific work but ensures that the project runs smoothly. Producing a safe environment for all the persons involved contributes to this objective.
- Very important to get a gender good balance and make each one keen to contribute.
- In my research study, as I am producing a numerical model of physical equations, I do not see how I can integrate it in my work. Nevertheless, in laboratories that would be interesting.
- Not so relevant for our common business when working in Italy; our gender related attention is good enough to ensure equality inside the working team; it can be relevant if and when we could provide consultancies in countries where the access to water is evidently gender discriminated; over there the impacts of our work could generate usually significant improvements.
- Our organisation stands for an innovative water sector, representing a dynamic environment where diverse perspectives are available to address water-related challenges from various angles. This includes perspectives from both the problem owners and solution providers. Our vision to build a Water-Smart Society relies on involving all stakeholders in the design, management, and implementation of the water governance system.
- I think gender equality play an important role in every job.
- Yes, it is important that in workshops, round tables etc. both men and women are equally represented.
- Very important, as in all STEM institutions.
- 8x yes
- No

(11 unanswered)

6) *Do you think your research/work could in any way pay more attention to the gender dimension?*

- 7x yes
- 2x I think we have included it when possible / in reasonable way
- 2x no
- Surely. Actually, answering this survey makes me even more conscious of the subject
- Gender dimension must be all time present in any of our activities; when gender is a sensitive issue for the specific case; we properly consider it during our work execution as also as one of the main co-design criteria.
- Maybe, but I do not yet know how to include gender data or results from gender studies in my work.
- Maybe, because sometimes jobs that require skill and meticulousness are more suitable for women than jobs that require strength like men.
- Yes, we should improve the ratio of researchers male vs female
- We are very attentive to this issue. Just as info: In our public body and in general in Italian public administrations there are many women among civil servants, but few in management (mainly male).

(11 unanswered)

Based on the answers received from partner organisations in the above-mentioned survey, as well as the work in the first two years of MULTISOURCE, additional information was gathered at the Annual Meeting in Milan to further understand the modus operandi regarding gender and other social issues.

The pilots that you work on / are involved in (mark all relevant answers) (N = 18)

- Focus on a single / very dominant primary environmental benefit: 39 %
- Includes the interplay of a few environmental benefits: 33 %
- Includes environmental, social & economic benefits: 22 %
- The project led me to think about other environmental benefits: 6 %
- The project led me to think about other social and economic benefits: 0 %

Do you think that talking about the social and gender dimensions is overrated?

- Yes: 15 %
- It is relevant only in very few occasions: 35 %
- No: 50 %

Do you think that your levels of knowledge are sufficient to deal with social justice and gender in your interventions?

- My knowledge is adequate: 0 %
- I don't always know how to think in terms of social justice relating to NBS: 73 %
- I would like to know more about it: 27 %

If you think the social dimension is important and you have knowledge, do you have dedicated time at work to do so? (N = 20)

- Always: 25 %
- Only sometimes: 25 %
- It is a task that I need to carry out in my free time: 50 %

What could be the next steps that would motivate you to further include the gender and social dimensions in your considerations?

- Funds
Funding / Funding, especially regarding developing countries
- New modus operandi
Assignments where enough time & money is available to include social aspects already in the planning and design stage and not only for communication / Involving social scientists into our work / Involvement of key groups that can inform (ie community groups, local initiatives) / More inclusive actions in R & I projects / New approaches into our research / Official recognition of the social dimension as a decisional item to be considered
- More knowledge
Training on how to include social and gender dimensions into our work / Knowing how to do it / Examples how to do it / Training on how to include perspectives of citizens
- Evidence that it has impact
Seeing a practical output and benefits / Comparing cultural or country water practices to get a broader view of the situation / Case studies that provide examples of what it means to include gender & social dimensions into NBS for water treatment / Understanding what is the impact when including & when not including gender and social dimensions in design, cooperation and maintenance of NBS

